

Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process

Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, Ramin Hashemi*

School of Mechanical Engineering, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran

*Corresponding author: rhashemi@iust.ac.ir (R. Hashemi)

Abstract

The wear phenomenon is one of the essential factors in the failure of industrial components. Therefore, it is vital to investigate the wear behavior of engineering materials and metal matrix composites (MMC). In this article, Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets were fabricated using the accumulative roll bonding (ARB) process. The ARB process was performed at ambient temperature without any heat treatment between the cycles in 5 passes. Mechanical properties, fracture surface, and wear behavior of the specimens were also measured. The tensile strength of the Al/Brass/Al sandwich sample is higher than the primary aluminum and less than the original brass. As the number of ARB cycles increases, the tensile strength and elongation changes have no significant trend. The highest ultimate tensile strength was obtained in the first cycle at 288 MPa, which is about 3.5 times the primary aluminum. The highest hardness was also obtained for aluminum and brass after the end of the fourth cycle. Pin-on-disk wear tests were applied with two different forces on specimens, and as an important achievement, the results show that by using Al/Brass/Al composite can increase the wear resistance of aluminum. Worn surface morphology and wear debris of samples were also examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The optical microscope's checking of the layers shows that the brass layer is completely crushed in the aluminum field from the second cycle onwards. Fracture surface images of the samples also show both ductile and brittle fractures.

Keywords: wear resistance, accumulative roll bonding (ARB), mechanical properties, metal matrix composite

1. Introduction

Nowadays, to increase the physical and mechanical properties of the materials, severe plastic deformation methods (SPD) have been considered. In the SPD process, by applying high strain to the material while maintaining the primary dimensions, ultrafine and nanostructured materials can be produced [1]. So far, a lot of research has been done on a variety of SPD processes: Cyclic Extrusion Compression (CEC) [2,3], Equal-Channel Angular Pressing (ECAP) [4]–[6], High-Pressure Torsion (HPT) [7,8], Equal-Channel Angular Rolling (ECAR) [9,10] and ARB [11]–[13]. Among the methods mentioned, ARB has become more popular due to the ease of the process and no need for expensive equipment and molds [14]. Various parameters affect the accumulative roll bonding process. Li et al. [15] studied the initial thickness of sheets used in ARB and found that

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, Journal of Manufacturing Processes, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

at a constant thickness decrease, the bond strength decreased with increasing initial thickness. Jamaati et al. [16] examined the percentage of thickness reduction. The result was that by increasing the decrease in thickness of the sheets, bond strength improved. They also checked the impact of heat treatment before and after the process, and they realized that pre and post-annealing help increase bond strength. In another study, Rai et al. [17] examined the influence of annealing temperature and annealing time on bond strength. They found that by increasing temperature and time, the quality of the bond improves. Delshad et al. [12] investigated the influence of temperature on the formability and mechanical properties of aluminum sheets produced by ARB. The results showed that by increasing the temperature of the sheets before rolling to 300 ° C, relative to room temperature, elongation increases by about 38%. Su et al. [18] discussed the effect of strain on the accumulative roll bonding process and found that by enhancing the effective strain to the sheet, yield strength, hardness, and bond strength increased, and the fracture strain decreased. Research on the type and amount of reinforcing particles has had different results. Alizadeh and Paydar [19] showed that TiO₂ particles reduce bond strength. While Lu et al. [20] found that bond strength increased for SiO₂ particles. Wu et al. [21] examined the crystal structure of metals. they noticed that the closer the elastic deformation of the two metals are to each other, cold roll bonding with higher strength and lower residual stress would be possible. Much research has also been performed on the mechanical and metallurgical characteristics of sheets made by this method [22]–[25].

Due to the high maintenance costs, the wear properties of components have always been of paramount importance. The most common way to reduce wear is to use high wear resistance coatings that are relatively expensive. In recent years, efforts have been made to increase the wear resistance of materials using metallurgical changes in their structure. In the meantime, the impact of SPD processes on wear resistance as a new method has attracted the attention of researchers. For example, the results showed that the ECAE/P process slightly reduced the wear [26]. Research has shown that the HPT process improves the wear behavior of materials [27,28]. Studies have also been conducted on the effect of the ARB process on the wear rate: Sadeghinia et al. [29] investigated the wear behavior of Al/Ti ultrafine-grained multilayered sheet manufactured by ARB. They found that until the sixth cycle, there was no substantial enhancement in the wear resistance of the specimens. But from cycle eight onwards, the wear rate decreases due to changes in the wear mechanism. Baharipour et al. [30] studied the wear properties of AL strips with Ni reinforcing particles fabricated by the ARB method. They understood that as the number of process cycles and the amount of nickel particles increase, wear resistance improves. Eizadjou et al. [31] checked the wear behavior of ARBed 6061 aluminum alloy. They realized that the ARB process increases the wear rate. Jamaati et al. [32] fabricated the nanostructured Al/Al₂O₃ composite using the ARB process to study wear behavior. The results were that the ARB method rises the wear rate and thereby reduces the wear resistance. According to the literature review mentioned above, in the vast majority of cases, the accumulative roll bonding process has a negative effect on wear resistance. Various reasons such as increasing hardness and decreasing ductility have been identified for the sharp increase in wear rate after the ARB process [33]. In other words, the annealed sample has a lower wear rate due to its lower hard work capability [34]. However, in higher cycles, the formation and increase of high angle grain boundaries (HAGB) are the main factors in reducing wear resistance [35].

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, Journal of Manufacturing Processes, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

In this research, for the first time, the wear properties of aluminum/brass/aluminum composite made by ARB technique were investigated. It was shown without the use of nanoparticles and by using a different and accessible metal (brass), in addition to significantly increasing the tensile strength, the wear rate of aluminum can also be reduced. This result can be used in situations where aluminum wear is critical.

2.Experimental procedure

In this study, aluminum 1050 and brass (70/30) were used. After the quantometer test, the chemical composition of the materials was determined as Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of Al 1050 and Brass 70/30

material	chemical composition (wt%)							
	Al	Zn	Mg	Ti	Mn	Fe	Si	Cu
Aluminum 1050	99.421	0.016	0.006	0.018	0.029	0.286	0.115	0.084
Brass 70/30	Cu	Zn	Pb	Sn	Ni	Fe	S	Al
	69.63	30.01	0.004	0.104	0.085	0.04	0.01	0.009

Initial thicknesses for aluminum and brass were 1.5 mm and 1 mm, respectively. The samples must first be annealed to prepare the sheets for the accumulative roll bonding process. For this purpose, aluminum and brass sheets are heated at 400° C and 550 ° C for one hour, respectively. This eliminates any potential work hardening from the manufacturing process and achieves a homogeneous structure. After cutting the sheets to 150 x 60 mm, the samples are cleaned by acetone. Then, to remove the oxide layer and the remaining contaminants, the specimens' surface is scratched by a wire brush. Next, the prepared surfaces are overlapped with thin copper wire. The samples are immediately rolled by applying 50% reductions, and the Al/Brass/Al sandwich is produced. The steps mentioned above must be performed continuously to achieve a high-quality bond. After the fabrication of the first sandwich, to attainment higher cycles, the sample is divided into two equal sections (in the longitudinal direction) ,and the steps are repeated. The process was carried out in 5 cycles (sandwich and 4 ARB cycle) at ambient temperature without any heat treatment between the cycles. For this purpose, a rolling machine with a capacity of 30 tons with a rolling diameter of 200 mm and a speed of 10 rpm was used. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the ARB technique.

Fig.1 Schematic illustration of the ARB method.

After the fabrication of multilayer composites by the ARB method, microhardness tests and uniaxial tensile tests were performed. Vickers microhardness was measured according to the ASTM E384 standard in line with the thickness for each layer of Al and Br. The tests were done at five different points under 200 g loading and a duration of 10 seconds by the JENUS apparatus. Their average was reported as the final hardness after deleting outliers to eliminate possible errors. Three tensile test specimens were machined along the rolling direction to obtain elongation and tensile strength of composites. The tensile test was done at room temperature and strain rate $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ by SANTAM device.

The fracture surface was checked out by SEM to determine the type of fracture. The microstructure and composition of the layers were observed using optical microscopy. Pin on disk test was used to investigate the wear behavior of Al/Brass/Al composite sheets fabricated by ARB. In this test, disk specimens with a diameter of 30 mm are inserted into the machine, and then the disks are abraded by pins. The wear test was performed with two forces of 10N and 15N at a distance of 1000 m. Subsequently, worn surface morphology and wear debris of samples were also examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microstructure and plastic instability

The surface of the samples was observed under the optical microscope to study the structure of the aluminum and brass layers after ARB. Figure 2 shows the microstructure of the layers of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite in various ARB cycles. As is evident, there is no fracture or plastic instability in the Al and Br layers in the sandwich cycle (Fig. 2(a)). As shown in Fig. 2(b), in the first cycle, gradually necking occurs in the layers of Br, but no rupture is observed. From the second cycle onwards, failure occurs entirely in the layers of Br. By increasing the number of ARB process cycles, the plastic strain applied to the specimen increases, and the brass layer becomes shattered. According to previous research, fractures in one layer often occur in the bonding of dissimilar metals [36,37]. In fact, during the deformation of different metals due to

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, Journal of Manufacturing Processes, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

different flow properties and differences in the layers' mechanical properties, plastic instability occurs when the hard phases start to necking and eventually fracture [21]. This phenomenon can be due to differences in the amount of stacking fault energy (SFE) of the aluminum and brass [29]. In low-SFE materials such as brass, twinning is the main deformation mechanism. Therefore, at equal strains, the deformation will be easier for aluminum than brass, causing plastic instability in the brass [38]–[40].

Fig. 2 Microstructure of the layers of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite in various ARB cycles: a) sandwich, b) first cycle, c) second cycle, d) third cycle and e) the fourth cycle.

3.2. Mechanical properties

Figure 3 shows the strain-stress diagrams of pure aluminum, brass 70/30, and Al/Brass/Al multilayer composites processed by the ARB method. As can be seen, the yield strength of the Al/Brass/Al sandwich sample was obtained 246 MPa, which is higher than that of the primary aluminum and lower than that of the original brass. The elongation also decreased sharply compared to the primary sheets. This decline in elongation is due to the work hardening created during rolling, which increases the density of dislocations [41]–[43]. For better comparison, Figure 4 shows the strain-stress diagrams of Al/Brass/Al composite in various ARB cycles. According to Figure 4, the elongation and tensile strength in the first cycle compared to the sandwich sample increased and decreased, respectively, so that the highest possible ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was obtained after the first cycle (288 MPa), that is 350% more than annealed aluminum. In addition to the density of dislocations, grain refinement strengthening and interface strengthening can increase the yield strength during the ARB technique [44]. Also, by increasing cycles, the number of interfaces increases steadily, which can be used as a barrier to prevent dislocations and thus improve strength. This phenomenon is visible from the second cycle onwards.

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves of pure aluminum, brass 70/30, and Al/Brass/Al multilayer composites processed by ARB process.

Fig. 4 Stress-strain diagrams of Al/Brass/Al composite in various ARB cycles.

With an increasing number of ARB process cycles, changes in tensile strength and elongation are not a clear trend. As mentioned in the preceding section, plastic instability and fracture in the second cycle occur in the brass layer. Therefore, the reduction of tensile strength in the second cycle can be justified by this phenomenon. From the second cycle onwards, the distribution of crushed brass in aluminum is improved, and as a result, tensile strength increases. However, increasing the density of the dislocations at this stage is also effective in increasing the tensile strength. This trend continues until the end of the fourth cycle, but the tensile strength is still lower than the sandwich cycle sample. Figure 5 displays the variation of elongation and ultimate tensile strength for various cycles of the ARB process.

Fig. 5 Variation of elongation and UTS for different cycles of the ARB process.

In general, it seems that the improvement of mechanical properties during the ARB method is due to two mechanisms of strain hardening and grain refinement. In primary cycles, the strain hardening mechanism plays the leading role, so the maximum increase in tensile strength also occurs in the first cycle [45]. As the number of process cycles increases due to the displacement density's saturation, the strain hardening effect gradually decreases, and the grain refinement will be an essential factor in the elongation and strength changes. Therefore, the enhancement of mechanical properties in the final cycles is probably due to the grain-refinement and proper distribution of brass in the aluminum field.

Figure 6 shows the Vickers microhardness test results for each layer of aluminum and brass in various ARB cycles. As it is known, microhardness increases during the accumulative roll bonding process. This is because as the number of ARB cycles increases, the strain applied and dislocation density increases [46]–[48]. The highest growth in the microhardness was observed after the sandwich cycle, which aluminum and brass grew by 52% and 94%, respectively, compared to the annealed sample. Again, the difference in SFE of Al and Br seems to be The main reason for the difference in the hardness growth of the two metals [49]. After the sandwich cycle, the rate of increase in hardness becomes smoother due to saturation of the dislocation density.

Fig. 6 Variation of hardness for each layer of aluminum and brass in different ARB cycles.

3.3. Wear behavior

To evaluate the wear behavior, a pin on the disk test was performed with 10 N and 15 N forces at a sliding distance of 1000 m and a sliding speed of 0.12 m/s . By measuring the weight of the specimens before and after the test, we can obtain weight loss and other wear properties. Figure 7 shows the weight loss of annealed and composite samples processed by the ARB technique in various cycles at two forces. As shown in Fig. 7, as the number of ARB process cycles increases, the amount of weight loss decreases, and the wear resistance improves.

Fig. 7 The weight loss of annealed and composite samples processed by ARB technique in various cycles at two forces.

Fig. 8 The wear rate of annealed and composite samples processed by ARB technique in various cycles at two forces.

Figure 8 shows the wear rate of the tested samples. In the annealed state, the specimens have the lowest strength and hardness and therefore have high wear rates. In fact, under unprocessed conditions, the samples are easily abraded by a pin, and the debris particles are formed [50]. However, it was evident that brass metal has a much lower wear rate than aluminum due to its inherent mechanical and physical properties. According to Figure 8, the wear rate of the sandwich

cycle is lower than that of the primary aluminum sample, and with increasing process cycles, this downward trend is maintained. In fact, in higher cycles, the hardness value increases, and therefore the wear rate decreases [29,51]. Also, a more homogeneous distribution of Br in the composite improves the microstructural refinement and increases the sub-boundaries, reducing the wear rate [52]. At the same applied load (15N), the most wear rate changes compared to primary aluminum were observed after the sandwich cycle at 21%. For the second and fourth cycles, this change was 10% and 9%, respectively. However, at the end of the fourth cycle, the wear rate reaches its lowest level, which decreased by 35% compared to the unprocessed sample. Using an adhesion asperity deformation model, Archard [53] presented an equation for the wear volume:

$$V = \frac{KNL}{3H} \quad (1)$$

Where V is the wear volume during the test, N is the applied load, L is the sliding distance, K is a wear coefficient, and H is the hardness of the wearing surface. To fit experimental results, K has to be allowed to vary over an immense range (10^{-2} – 10^{-8}) [54].

According to Equation (1), as the applied load increases, the wear volume increases, which corresponds to the experimental results shown in Figure 7 (the weight loss at 15N is higher than 10N). Also, a decrease in weight loss with increasing hardness can be justified by using Equation (1). Based on the topics discussed, it can be concluded that two factors of hardness and structure refinement affect the wear rate of Al/Brass/Al composite sheets fabricated by ARB process [55]. In early cycles, increasing hardness is the leading cause of the reduction in wear rates, whereas, in higher cycles, structure refinement is the dominant mechanism. To understand the wear mechanism, Figures 9 and 10 show worn surface morphology and wear debris. In general, it can be said that three primary mechanisms for sliding wear are known: Adhesion, Abrasion, and Surface fatigue. Furthermore, many factors such as hardness, crystal structure, yield strength, work hardening, resistance to crack nucleation can affect sliding wear [56,57]. In addition to these three mechanisms, the delimitation theory can well explain many phenomena of wear. It is based on dislocation theory; the plastic deformation and fracture near the surface explain the wear debris formation [58]. Due to the large cracks and pits caused by high deformation, it is clear that the main mechanism of wear in annealed aluminum (Fig. 9(a)) is delamination. Therefore, the wear rate in this sample is very high. Also, for the Brass sample, the abrasion lines with the presence of scratches are visible, indicating abrasive and adhesion mechanisms. The wear rate of these mechanisms is much lower than that of the delamination mechanism [59]. In specimens processed by ARB, the worn surfaces are similar to the annealed aluminum sample except that the intensity of the delamination mechanism is less. Instead, the abrasive mechanism is more dominant (Fig. 9(e)). The dominant mechanism in the final cycles is a combination of abrasion and adhesion [55]. As the number of ARB cycles increases, the composite layer structure and the number of interfaces increase [32]. Also, due to the unstable grain boundaries created during the ARB method, recrystallization and coarsening of the seeds may occur, which reduces wear resistance [51]. For these two reasons, and according to previous research, the wear rate is expected to increase in higher cycles, but our results recorded a declining trend in final cycles. The reason for this contradiction may be that in this study, Br was used as the sandwich core. Brass can support aluminum as a hard layer and reduce wear rates and change the dominant wear mechanism from

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, Journal of Manufacturing Processes, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>
delamination to abrasion. This achievement can be used as a practical solution to improve wear resistance.

Fig. 9 SEM micrograph worn surface morphology of (a, b) annealed Al (c, d) annealed Br (e, f) sandwich and (g, h) fourth cycle of ARB, in two different magnifications.

Wear debris is usually formed in the early stages of wear, and their formation has a significant impact on the wear rate. So that by studying the morphology of this debris, we can find out the wear mechanism. The differences in the size of the primary Al and Br debris are clearly illustrated in Figure 10 (a) and (b). The smaller wear debris indicates the abrasive mechanism's dominance and, therefore, the lower wear rate. The debris size becomes smaller after the ARB process, and this behavior becomes more prominent in the final cycle (Figure 10 (d)). A combination of small and large debris in the fourth cycle of ARB indicates both delamination and abrasive mechanisms. It seems that the amount of debris determines the main mechanism. However, definitive conclusions in this discussion need further investigation.

Fig. 10 Wear debris morphology of samples a) annealed Al, b) annealed Br, c) sandwich, and d) the fourth cycle of ARB.

To compare more precisely, Table 2 shows the influence of ARB on the wear behavior of various materials.

Table 2. Influence of ARB on the wear behavior of various materials in past research

<i>Material</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Number of ARB cycles</i>	<i>Effect of ARB on wear behavior</i>	<i>The improvement compared to the annealed sample</i>	<i>REF</i>
<i>Al</i>	2005	7	samples produced by ARB had low wear resistance	NO	[60]
<i>Al</i>	2008	8	the weight loss until the third cycle decreases and then increases	NO	[61]
<i>Al</i>	2009	8	the wear rate until the third cycle decreases and then increases	NO	[51]
<i>Al</i>	2011	5	the weight loss until the fourth cycle drops and then increases	NO	[31]
<i>Al</i>	2011	8	the wear rate until the third cycle decreases and then increases	NO	[35]
<i>Al/Sic</i>	2013	10	as the number of ARB cycles increases, the amount of weight loss steadily decreases	YES	[50]
<i>Al/Al₂O₃</i>	2014	11	as the number of ARB cycles increases, the wear resistance of the composite and monolithic specimens decreases	NO	[32]
<i>Cu/Zn</i>	2014	8	heat treatment after an ARB process increases the amount of weight loss and wear rate.	-----	[62]
<i>Al/Ni_p</i>	2015	7	the wear rate until the third cycle decreases and then increases	NO	[30]
<i>Al/Ti</i>	2019	10	the wear rate decreases until the eighth cycle and then increases	YES	[29]
<i>Al/Br/Al</i>	2020	5	as the number of ARB cycles increases, the wear rate steadily decreases	YES	This study

3.4. Fractography

Figure 11 illustrates the fracture surface of the samples after the tensile test. The presence of deep equiaxed dimples in the annealed samples indicates ductile fracture (Fig. 1 (a) and (b)). Due to the low density of dislocations in the annealed sample as well as the Aluminum and Brass 70/30 FCC structure, this type of fracture is common [63]. The presence of deeper dimples in the Brass indicates higher ductility than aluminum, consistent with the results of the tensile test. After the sandwich cycle, the dimples become shallower and elongated, showing ductile shear fracture. The shape and orientation of the dimples indicate the type and direction of loading, respectively. In the higher cycle of the ARB process, Non-uniform plastic strain causes shear loads; thus, the dimples are elongated. The final fracture occurs due to the internal shear between the micro-cavities and the dimples present in shear stress [46]. As shown in Figure 11(e), at the end of the fourth cycle, shallow small elongated shear dimples are visible, which are in the shear direction. This rupture mode involves internal shearing between voids [64].

Fig.15 Tensile fracture surfaces of (a) annealed Al (b) annealed Br (c) sandwich (d) second cycle and (e) fourth cycle of ARB.

4. Conclusions

In this study, mechanical properties, wear behavior and fracture surface of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets produced by ARB were investigated. The following is a summary of the results:

- 1- From the second cycle onwards, failure occurs in brass layers. It can be due to differences in the amount of SFE of Al and Brass. By increasing the ARB cycles, the plastic strain applied to the specimen increases, and the brass layer becomes shattered.
- 2- The highest possible UTS was obtained after the first cycle (288 MPa), which is 350% more than annealed aluminum. After the first cycle, the tensile strength and elongation decrease noticeably, and then these values increase again as the number of process cycles increases. These changes are due to rupture in the layers of brass and improvement of its distribution in the field of aluminum.
- 3- Results showed that as the number of cycles increased, the wear rate decreased. The reason for the improvement in wear resistance is the change of the main mechanism from delamination to abrasion in the final cycles. Examination of the size and morphology of wear debris also confirms this phenomenon.
- 4- Investigation of the fracture surface illustrates that by increasing the ARB cycles, shallow small elongated shear dimples are visible, which indicates a ductile shear fracture.

References

- [1] D. Rahmatabadi, A. Shahmirzaloo, M. Farahani, M. Tayyebi, and R. Hashemi, "Characterizing the elastic and plastic properties of the multilayered Al/Brass composite produced by ARB using DIC," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 753, pp. 70–78, 2019.
- [2] Y. J. Chen, Q. D. Wang, H. J. Roven, M. Karlsen, Y. D. Yu, M. P. Liu, J. Hjelen., "Microstructure evolution in magnesium alloy AZ31 during cyclic extrusion compression," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 462, no. 1, pp. 192–200, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2007.07.116.
- [3] W. Guo, Q. Wang, B. Ye, X. Li, X. Liu, and H. Zhou, "Microstructural refinement and homogenization of Mg–SiC nanocomposites by cyclic extrusion compression," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 556, pp. 267–270, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2012.06.086.
- [4] M. Furukawa, Y. Iwahashi, Z. Horita, M. Nemoto, and T. G. Langdon, "The shearing characteristics associated with equal-channel angular pressing," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 257, no. 2, pp. 328–332, Dec. 1998, doi: 10.1016/S0921-5093(98)00750-3.
- [5] G. S. Dyakonov, S. Mironov, I. P. Semenova, R. Z. Valiev, and S. L. Semiatin, "EBSD analysis of grain-refinement mechanisms operating during equal-channel angular pressing of commercial-purity titanium," *Acta Mater.*, vol. 173, pp. 174–183, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.actamat.2019.05.014.
- [6] K. Bryła, J. Horky, M. Krystian, L. Lityńska-Dobrzyńska, and B. Mingler, "Microstructure, mechanical properties, and degradation of Mg-Ag alloy after equal-channel angular pressing," *Mater. Sci. Eng. C*, vol. 109, p. 110543, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.msec.2019.110543.
- [7] A. P. Zhilyaev and T. G. Langdon, "Using high-pressure torsion for metal processing: Fundamentals and applications," *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 893–979, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.pmatsci.2008.03.002.
- [8] A. P. Zhilyaev, S. Lee, G. V Nurislamova, R. Z. Valiev, and T. G. Langdon, "Microhardness and microstructural evolution in pure nickel during high-pressure torsion," *Scr. Mater.*, vol. 44, no. 12, pp. 2753–2758, 2001, doi:10.1016/S1359-6462(01)00955-1.
- [9] C. Y. Nam, J. H. Han, Y. H. Chung, and M. C. Shin, "Effect of precipitates on microstructural evolution of 7050 Al alloy sheet during equal channel angular rolling," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 347, no. 1, pp. 253–257, Apr. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0921-5093(02)00597-X.
- [10] J. E. Bozcheloei, M. Sedighi, and R. Hashemi, "The effect of temperature on the mechanical properties and forming limit diagram of Al 5083 produced by equal channel angular rolling," *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 2019 10510, vol. 105, no. 10, pp. 4389–4400, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1007/S00170-019-04586-1.
- [11] Y. Saito, H. Utsunomiya, N. Tsuji, and T. Sakai, "Novel ultra-high straining process for bulk materials development of the accumulative roll-bonding (ARB) process," *Acta Mater.*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 579–583, Jan. 1999, doi: 10.1016/S1359-6454(98)00365-6.

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

- [12] M. D. Gholami, R. Hashemi, and M. Sedighi, "The effect of temperature on the mechanical properties and forming limit diagram of aluminum strips fabricated by accumulative roll bonding process" *J. Mater. Res. Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1831–1846, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jmrt.2019.12.016.
- [13] D. Rahmatabadi, R. Hashemi, B. Mohammadi, and T. Shojaei, "Experimental evaluation of the plane stress fracture toughness for ultra-fine grained aluminum specimens prepared by accumulative roll bonding process," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 708, pp. 301–310, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2017.09.085.
- [14] H. Pirgazi, A. Akbarzadeh, R. Petrov, and L. Kestens, "Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of AA1100 aluminum sheet processed by accumulative roll bonding," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 497, no. 1–2, pp. 132–138, 2008.
- [15] L. Li, K. Nagai, and F. Yin, "Progress in cold roll bonding of metals," *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 23001, 2008.
- [16] R. Jamaati and M. R. Toroghinejad, "Cold roll bonding bond strengths," *Mater. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 1101–1108, 2011.
- [17] M. Raei, M. R. Toroghinejad, R. Jamaati, and J. A. Szpunar, "Effect of ARB process on textural evolution of AA1100 aluminum alloy," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 527, no. 26, pp. 7068–7073, 2010.
- [18] L. Su, C. Lu, A. K. Tieu, G. Deng, and X. Sun, "Ultrafine grained AA1050/AA6061 composite produced by accumulative roll bonding," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 559, pp. 345–351, 2013.
- [19] M. Alizadeh and M. H. Paydar, "Study on the effect of presence of TiH₂ particles on the roll bonding behavior of aluminum alloy strips," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 82–86, 2009.
- [20] C. Lu, K. Tieu, and D. Wexler, "Significant enhancement of bond strength in the accumulative roll bonding process using nano-sized SiO₂ particles," *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, vol. 209, no. 10, pp. 4830–4834, 2009.
- [21] K. Wu, H. Chang, E. Maawad, W. M. Gan, H. G. Brokmeier, and M. Y. Zheng, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of the Mg/Al laminated composite fabricated by accumulative roll bonding ARB," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 527, no. 13–14, pp. 3073–3078, 2010.
- [22] S. Tamimi, M. Ketabchi, and N. Parvin, "Microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of accumulative roll bonded interstitial free steel," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 2556–2562, 2009.
- [23] P. D. Motevalli and B. Eghbali, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of Tri-metal Al/Ti/Mg laminated composite processed by accumulative roll bonding," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 628, pp. 135–142, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2014.12.067.
- [24] D. Rahmatabadi, M. Pahlavani, M. D. Gholami, J. Marzbanrad, and R. Hashemi, "Production of Al/Mg-Li composite by the accumulative roll bonding process," *J. Mater. Res. Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 7880–7886, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JMRT.2020.05.084.
- [25] M. Sedighi, P. Farhadipour, and M. Heydari Vini, "Mechanical Properties and Microstructural Evolution of Bimetal 1050/Al₂O₃ /5083 Composites Fabricated by Warm Accumulative Roll Bonding," *JOM*, vol. 68, no. 12, pp. 3193–3200, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11837-016-2123-7.

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

- [26] T. Kucukomeroglu, "Effect of equal-channel angular extrusion on mechanical and wear properties of eutectic Al-12Si alloy," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 782-789, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.MATDES.2009.08.004.
- [27] C. Gode, H. Yilmazer, I. Ozdemir, and Y. Todaka, "Microstructural refinement and wear property of Al-Si-Cu composite subjected to extrusion and high-pressure torsion," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 618, pp. 377-384, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2014.09.011.
- [28] K. Edalati, M. Ashida, Z. Horita, T. Matsui, and H. Kato, "Wear resistance and tribological features of pure aluminum and Al-Al₂O₃ composites consolidated by high-pressure torsion," *Wear*, vol. 310, no. 1-2, pp. 83-89, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.WEAR.2013.12.022.
- [29] H. Sadeghinia, H. R. Jafarian, M. T. Salehi, and A. R. Eivani, "Comprehensive investigation on wear and microstructure development in Al/Ti ultrafine grained multi-layered composite produced by Accumulative Roll Bonding (ARB)," *Mater. Res. Express*, vol. 6, no. 11, p. 116572, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1088/2053-1591/AB49E3.
- [30] H. Baharipour, H. Daneshmanesh, and F. Ghanbari Mardasi, "Mechanical and wear properties of Al-Nip composites produced by ARB process," *Iran. J. Mater. Form.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 44-53, 2015.
- [31] M. Eizadjou, A. K. Talachi, H. D. Manesh, and K. Janghorban, "Sliding wear behavior of severely deformed 6061 aluminum alloy by accumulative roll bonding ARB process," in *Materials Science Forum*, 2011, vol. 667, pp. 1107-1112.
- [32] R. Jamaati, M. Naseri, and M. R. Toroghinejad, "Wear behavior of nanostructured Al/Al₂O₃ composite fabricated via accumulative roll bonding ARB process," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 59, pp. 540-549, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2014.03.027.
- [33] S. Ghalehandi, M. Malaki, M. G.-A. Sciences, and undefined 2019, "Accumulative roll bonding—a review," *mdpi.com*, doi: 10.3390/app9173627.
- [34] N. Gao, Ch. T. Wang, R. J. K. Wood, T. G. Langdon, "Tribological properties of ultrafine-grained materials processed by severe plastic deformation," *J Mater Sci*, vol. 47, no. 12, pp. 4779-4797, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s10853-011-6231-z.
- [35] A. K. Talachi, M. Eizadjou, H. D. Manesh, and K. Janghorban, "Wear characteristics of severely deformed aluminum sheets by accumulative roll bonding ARB process," *Mater. Charact.*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 12-21, 2011.
- [36] M. Hosseini, N. Pardis, H. Danesh Manesh, M. Abbasi, and D.-I. Kim, "Structural characteristics of Cu/Ti bimetal composite produced by accumulative roll-bonding ARB," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 113, pp. 128-136, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2016.09.094.
- [37] M. Reihanian and M. Naseri, "An analytical approach for necking and fracture of hard layer during accumulative roll bonding ARB of metallic multilayer," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 89, pp. 1213-1222, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2015.10.088.
- [38] A. Mozaffari, H. D. Manesh, and K. Janghorban, "Evaluation of mechanical properties and structure of multilayered Al/Ni composites produced by accumulative roll bonding ARB process," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 489, no. 1, pp. 103-109, 2010.
- [39] R. Jamaati, M. R. Toroghinejad, and H. Edris, "Effect of stacking fault energy on nanostructure formation under accumulative roll bonding ARB process," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 578, pp. 191-

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>
196, Aug. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2013.04.090.

- [40] D. Rahmatabadi, M. Tayyebi, R. Hashemi, and G. Faraji, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of Al/Cu/Mg laminated composite sheets produced by the ARB process," *Int. J. Miner. Metall. Mater.*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 564–572, 2018.
- [41] D. Rahmatabadi and R. Hashemi, "Experimental evaluation of forming limit diagram and mechanical properties of nano/ultra-fine grained aluminum strips fabricated by accumulative roll bonding," *Int. J. Mater. Res.*, vol. 108, no. 12, pp. 1036–1044, 2017.
- [42] H. R. Jafarian, S. H. M. Anijdan, A. R. Eivani, and N. Park, "A comprehensive study of microstructure development and its corresponding tensile properties in nano/ultrafine-grained metastable austenitic steel during accumulative roll bonding ARB," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 703, pp. 196–204, 2017.
- [43] M. D. Gholami, D. Rahmatabadi, T. Shojaee, R. Hashemi, and B. Mohammadi, "The role of applied strain and volume percentage of components on mechanical properties and fracture toughness in multilayered Al/Mg composite fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process," *Mater. Res. Express*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 026508, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1088/2053-1591/ABE103.
- [44] Z. Wei, H. Zheng, R. Wu, J. Zhang, H. Wu, S. Jin, Y. Jiao, L. Hou, "Interface behavior and tensile properties of Mg-14Li-3Al-2Gd sheets prepared by four-layer accumulative roll bonding," *J. Manuf. Process.*, vol. 61, pp. 254–260, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JMAPRO.2020.11.021.
- [45] D. Rahmatabadi, M. Tayyebi, A. Sheikhi, and R. Hashemi, "Fracture toughness investigation of Al1050/Cu/MgAZ31ZB multi-layered composite produced by accumulative roll bonding process," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 734, pp. 427–436, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.MSEA.2018.08.017.
- [46] M. Naseri, M. Reihanian, and E. Borhani, "Effect of strain path on microstructure, deformation texture and mechanical properties of nano/ultrafine grained AA1050 processed by accumulative roll bonding ARB," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 673, pp. 288–298, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2016.07.031.
- [47] M. Alvand, M. Naseri, E. Borhani, and H. Abdollah-Pour, "Nano/ultrafine grained AA2024 alloy processed by accumulative roll bonding: a study of microstructure, deformation texture and mechanical properties," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 712, pp. 517–525, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2017.04.117.
- [48] M. H. Vini and M. Sedighi, "Mechanical properties and bond strength of bimetallic AA1050/AA5083 laminates fabricated by warm-accumulative roll bonding," *The Canadian Journal of Metallurgy and Materials Science*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 160–167, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1080/00084433.2017.1405539.
- [49] L. Ghalandari, M. M. Mahdavian, and M. Reihanian, "Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of Cu/Zn multilayer processed by accumulative roll bonding ARB," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 593, pp. 145–152, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2013.11.026.
- [50] E. Darmiani, I. Danaee, M. A. Golozar, M. R. Toroghinejad, A. Ashrafi, and A. Ahmadi, "Reciprocating wear resistance of Al–SiC nano-composite fabricated by accumulative roll bonding process," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 50, pp. 497–502, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2013.03.047.
- [51] M. Eizadjou, H. D. Manesh, and K. Janghorban, "Microstructure and mechanical properties of ultra-fine grains UFGs aluminum strips produced by ARB process," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 474, no. 1, pp. 406–415, Apr. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2008.06.161.

Preprint of Mohammad Delshad Gholami, Mohammad Salamat, [Ramin Hashemi](#), Study of mechanical properties and wear resistance of Al 1050/Brass (70/30)/Al 1050 composite sheets fabricated by the accumulative roll bonding process, *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, Volume 71, November 2021, Pages 407-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.09.032>

- [52] M. Ebrahimi, A. Zarei-Hanzaki, H. R. Abedi, M. Azimi, and S. S. Mirjavadi, "Correlating the microstructure to mechanical properties and wear behavior of an accumulative back extruded Al-Mg₂Si in-situ composite," *Tribol. Int.*, vol. 115, pp. 199–211, 2017.
- [53] J. F. Archard, "Contact and Rubbing of Flat Surfaces," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 24, no. 8, p. 981, Jun. 2004, doi: 10.1063/1.1721448.
- [54] Y. Yang, A. A. Torrance, and P. L. B. Oxley, "Modelling mechanical wear processes in metallic sliding friction," *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 29, no. 3, p. 600, 1996.
- [55] M. Ebrahimi, S. Attarilar, F. Djavanroodi, C. Gode, and H. S. Kim, "Wear properties of brass samples subjected to constrained groove pressing process," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 63, pp. 531–537, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2014.06.043.
- [56] K. Zum Gahr, *Microstructure and wear of materials*. 1987. book.
- [57] G. Stachowiak, *Wear: materials, mechanisms and practice*. 2006. book
- [58] S. Wen and P. Huang, *Principles of tribology*. 2012. book
- [59] R. L. Deuis, C. Subramanian, and J. M. Yellup, "Dry sliding wear of aluminium composites—{A} review," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 415–435, Jan. 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0266-3538(96)00167-4.
- [60] Y. S. Kim, J. S. Ha, and D. H. Shin, "Sliding wear characteristics of ultrafine-grained non-strain-hardening aluminum-magnesium alloys," in *Materials science forum*, 2005, vol. 475, pp. 401–404.
- [61] A. K. Talachi, M. Eizadjou, H. D. Manesh, and K. Janghorban, "Wear properties of 1100 Al alloy produced by accumulative roll bonding," *Int. J. Mod. Phys. B*, vol. 22, no. 18n19, pp. 2848–2857, 2008.
- [62] M. Reihanian, M. M. Mahdavian, and L. Ghalandari, "Fabrication of the Cu-Zn multilayer and Cu-Zn alloy by accumulative roll bonding ARB with an emphasis on the wear behavior," *Iran. J. Mater. Form.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 52–62, 2019.
- [63] S. Pasebani and M. R. Toroghinejad, "Nano-grained 70/30 brass strip produced by accumulative roll-bonding ARB process," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 527, no. 3, pp. 491–497, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2009.09.029.
- [64] I. Barsoum and J. Faleskog, "Rupture mechanisms in combined tension and shear—Experiments," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 1768–1786, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2006.09.031.